

Exploring the Relationship between Substance Abuse and Mental Health Disorders on youths in Bo City

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Abstract

Substance abuse is serious public health concern. Adolescents who do not receive enough social support are more likely to struggle with mental health issues and turn to drugs. Using secondary data from other journals and the National Drug Survey on youths, the aim of this study was to ascertain whether there was an association between mental health problems, social support, and substance abuse among youths and whether this association varies with age. The study was guided by the relational regulation theory of social support. This study investigated the association among young people with mental health issues and substance use, as well as the relationship between mental health issues and social support. The findings demonstrated a statistically significant correlation between substance use and social support, mental health problems and substance use, and mental health problems and social support. Stakeholders and the government may create targeted interventions by assessing the relationship between youngsters in the Sierra Leone Bo community's mental health issues, substance abuse, and social support. Enhancements in social support could lead to good social change as the government and its partners learn more about the relationship between substance use and mental health issues in young people and social support.

Keywords: Substance Abuse, Mental Health, Social Support, Drug

Introduction

In many nations across the world, substance misuse has grown to be a significant social and health issue (Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), 2018). Substance abuse is the primary source of the public health burden associated with the cycle of domestic violence, according to Keyes et al. (2010). Substance abuse is the risk factor that adds the most to this public health burden. According to Barret et al. (2017), people have always tried to use drugs to change how they feel. Some of these drugs and their applications are frequently discovered to be in a precarious position between acceptable medical use and drug addiction.

A large number of individuals who habitually abuse substances are also diagnosed with mental problems, and vice versa, according to Barrett et al. (2012) and Robichaud et al. (2003). According to Barrett et al. (2012), there is a roughly twofold increased risk of drug use problems (abuse or dependence) among individuals with anxiety disorders. According to Michael Olusegun Adejimi, 2021 Castel et al. (2008), drug or alcohol misuse is highly common among people who suffer from serious mental illnesses. According to Norman et al. (2010), people with severe mental disorders and drug addiction disorders typically experience stigma, legal issues, low education, unemployment, loneliness, poverty, and homelessness in comparison to those with severe mental disorders alone.

Similarly, people who abuse substances and develop mental disorders have more severe psychiatric symptoms, worse treatment results, and higher rates of health service utilization (Urbanoski et al., 2007). Fleury et al. (2014) verified that the most common reasons of substance misuse among users with severe mental problems are sociodemographic characteristics such age, gender, civil status, education, and occupation in both clinical and epidemiological investigations. Other socioeconomic aspects linked to

substance misuse include gender and cultural disparities (Tuchman, 2010). For instance, males tend to use substances at higher rates than females do, both in terms of general drug usage and drug dependency (Tuchman, 2010).

In addition, women experience mood and anxiety disorders at higher rates than men do, while men are more likely than women to suffer from antisocial personality disorder. All of these conditions are risk factors for substance misuse (Wustoff et al., 2015). (Michael Olusegun Adejimi, 2021)

Research has been done on the relationship between substance addiction, mental health issues, and social support in the adult population as a whole (Amosu et al., 2016; Zhuang & Wong, 2017). The basis for current interventions used for the population suffering from mental illness, such as identifying youths who are vulnerable to ensure prevention and putting in place early interventions which increased health outcomes, is a multitude of studies that were conducted in schools, communities, healthcare facilities, and prisons. In order to guarantee proper treatment and care management, additional interventions and therapies addressing mental health issues are required (Conway et al., 2018). (Michael Olusegun Adejimi, 2021)

Nasiri and Bandani (2017) investigated the relationship between mental health and social support among university students and discovered a rise in the number of students experiencing mental health problems. Despite the abundance of research on social support and substance use linked to mental health in the general population, there is a dearth of studies on substance abuse and its relationship to mental illness disorder or mental health problems among the young.

Another study by Ni et al. (2017) revealed that substance use, such as drinking and using illegal drugs, was associated with a higher risk of mental health issues for specific age groups, particularly teens. Social support, substance use, and mental health disorders or difficulties are related, according to Mason et al. (2014) and Shahdadi et al., and this association should be investigated to find potential risk factors. Research on drug abuse, social support, and mental health disorders or issues in youth is required, since the authors discovered that the rise in substance abuse among young adults has not been accompanied by a similar rise in social support. Maine Integrated Youth Health Survey (MIYHS; 2017).

Social support is linked to substance misuse. Substance misuse can have negative effects on a person's wellbeing, especially if it has damaged their relationships with friends and family (Staton, Royse, & Leukfeld, 2007). Social support is thought to act as a buffer for people going through life crises, so those with enough of it are less likely to start abusing drugs when things are tough (University of Minnesota, 2016). This is due to the fact that constructive social support fosters the positive behavior required to prevent drug usage.

Anxiety, depression, and suicide are among the mental health issues that substance usage is linked to (Amosu et al., 2016; Lerrisa et al., 2017; Mason et al., 2014). According to Henchoz et al. (2016), there are a number of health hazards associated with substance use that include mental health issues. Substance usage may affect certain physiological pathways that result in negative health effects. For example, using drugs that include nicotine has the potential to cause addiction, and addiction is linked to mental health issues.

In a study conducted in the northern region of Nigeria by Abdu-Raheem (2013), it was found that most of the teens studied began experimenting with alcohol, tobacco, and ephedrine in an attempt to manage their sleep or invigorate themselves. Rose et al. (1988) highlighted a number of factors that contribute to drug misuse, including pain and anxiety, parental background, ignorance and misinformation about the use of these drugs, the drive to conduct crimes, peer group influence, loneliness, and isolation. Chikere and Mayowa (2011) state that alcohol use is the most prevalent drug use among students and that many students who use alcohol had their first drink in a familial environment. The authors also found that many of the impacted students started drinking alcohol while they were between the ages of 16 and 20. (Michael Olusegun Adejimi, 2021)

Problem Statement

Prescription drug abuse for non-medical purposes is becoming be a global danger to law enforcement and public health, with opioids being the most harmful and responsible for 76% of deaths linked to drug use disorders (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime). (UNODC, 2018).

Substance misuse and mental health disorders are linked and represent a significant public health concern (Conway et al., 2018). People who have a weak social support network throughout time are more likely to experience mental health issues than people with a robust social support network (Holden et al., 2015). Inadequate social support can exacerbate substance use disorders. (Milner et al., 2016)

A small number of research have looked at the degree of social support that people with mental health issues receive (Mottershaw & Haworth, 2017) and the relationship that exists between drug abuse and mental health issues (Conway et al., 2018). Race and other demographic characteristics may influence young adults' access to health care services as well as their substance abuse and mental health issues (Conway et al., 2018). While the prevalence of substance abuse, mental health issues, and social support in the adult population have all been extensively studied, little is known about how social support affects substance use and abuse, mental health issues, and other health outcomes across age groups.

According to Aina et al. (2010), many teenagers in Sierra Leone are unaware of the negative effects of psychoactive substances, despite global concern and education about them. The main causes of substance abuse are recognized to be curiosity, peer pressure, and social pressure. Danjuma et al. (2016) claim that treatment and rehabilitation of individuals with substance use disorders account up a sizeable portion of the national budget of Sierra Leone. Still, the issue is under control. This study examines the relationship between substance usage and mental health disorders in Sierra Leone for that reason.

Drug abuse and usage are considered to be among the issues preventing Sierra Leone from transitioning from an impoverished to a developed nation, despite the government's best efforts to improve everyone's health for the sake of human rights as well as social and economic development (Nwannennaya & Abiodun, 2017). In light of this, the study aimed to close the information gap about the reasons behind Sierra Leone's high rate of substance usage. This study, in contrast to others, examined a range of factors related to substance usage in Sierra Leone.

Theoretical Perspective of Substance Abuse

Treatment for substance abuse was guided by the theories of self-medication put out by Khantzian (2017) and David (1974a). The hypothesis was created by Khantzian and David to diagnose and treat drug addiction issues. The self-medication was done in the context of regulation, where the self-medication matched the person's perception or comprehension of regulation. The notion might make more sense when substance use in public and quasi-public schools is examined in relation to self-medication. According to the self-medication theory, drug use has a deeper cause. The self-medication theory was first proposed by Khantzian and Duncan, although Fenichel (1945) and Rado (1957) hypothesized that pressure was a driving force behind drug usage. Contributors to this theory include Glover (1956) and Ronsenfeld (1965), among others.

According to the Khantzian model of self-medication, drug addiction arises from an inability to manage aggression. As a result, the drug addict turns to drugs to suppress their aggressive urge, which eventually culminates in physical dependence (Khantzian, 1997b, 1999). This self-medication notion was first applied to cocaine, then to alcoholism, and finally it was transformed into a theory (Khantzian, 1997a, 1999). According to the fully developed theory of self-medication, drug addiction is the outcome of long-standing self-medication (Achalu, 2002). Based on behavioral theory, Duncan's (1974a) interpretation of self-medication distinguishes between drug use and drug misuse. According to Duncan, the majority of drug users are in control of their drug usage, and many illegal drug users do not meet the criteria for being classified as substance abusers.

According to Duncan's concept, using drugs without a prescription puts a person's health at danger. Duncan insisted that drug use is a result of the drug's enjoyable effects. Drug dependence, a word adopted to replace

the term addiction, was attempted to be explained by Duncan's model. The idea will assist in explaining why young people are using drugs, which pose a health risk and can result in mental health issues.

Substance/Drug Abuse in Sierra Leone

Drug abuse in Sierra Leone is becoming a bigger problem, made worse by the country's socioeconomic problems, high young unemployment rate, and trauma from the conflict. The increase in the use of drugs such as cocaine, marijuana, and more recent synthetic drugs is one of the main problems. The spread of illicit narcotics endangers people's health, safety, and financial stability.

Cannabis may be grown in Sierra Leone because of its climate, yet marijuana is still the most often overused narcotic, particularly among young people. Peer pressure, unemployment, and poverty are frequently associated with its use. Particularly in urban areas like Bo city, Sierra Leone has witnessed a rise in the availability and consumption of hard drugs like cocaine and heroin due to its status as a transit country in the global drug trade. Because they are readily available and reasonably priced, newer synthetic medicines like Kush and Tramadol are gaining popularity. The misuse of Kush and tramadol has been identified as a serious public health issue that affects young people, cab drivers, and even some school-age children. (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021)

Many young people, including former soldiers, experience psychological trauma as a result of the civil conflict that lasted from 1991 to 2002. Substance misuse has evolved into a coping mechanism for unemployment and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Because of the high unemployment rate in the nation, especially for young people, a lot of them turn to drugs as a way to cope and get money (via drug trafficking). Notwithstanding legislation that prohibit drug trafficking and use, enforcement of these laws is lax, permitting the sale of drugs in public areas sometimes even in close proximity to youth centers and schools. (World Drug Report 2020)

Concerns regarding substance abuse's effects on young people and society at large have made it a major public health and social issue in Sierra Leone. Substance addiction, including that of cannabis (known as "diamba"), Kush, tramadol, cocaine, heroin, and other drugs has become more prevalent, particularly in urban areas like Bo city. This misuse has been connected to a number of socioeconomic and health issues.

Substance addiction is now a significant public health and social issue in Sierra Leone due to worries about its consequences on youth and society at large. Substance addiction has increased, especially in urban places like Bo city. This includes addiction to cannabis (also known as "diamba"), Kush, tramadol, cocaine, heroin, and other narcotics. Numerous socioeconomic and health problems have been linked to this usage. (World Drug Report 2020)

The rising issue of drug misuse in Sierra Leone is caused by a number of reasons, including: Due to extreme poverty, high unemployment, and limited educational prospects, a large number of young people turn to drug usage as a coping method. Due to the nation's long history of civil war, many people—especially young men—have unresolved trauma. Abuse of substances is frequently utilized as a way to get over these psychological wounds. The legal system in Sierra Leone is inadequate in addressing drug trafficking and misuse, and the laws that are in place are not strictly enforced. This has made it possible for drug smuggling to grow, especially given its weak borders. In Sierra Leone, drug usage has had a disastrous effect on public health. Substance abusers frequently have mental health issues such as psychosis, anxiety, and sadness. The nation's brittle healthcare system faces challenges. (World Drug Report 2020)

Furthermore, drug use has been connected to a rise in violent crimes, especially involving young people in urban gangs. Additionally, research suggests that drug use has been linked to an increase in unsafe sexual activities, which in turn has accelerated the spread of HIV/AIDS and other STDs. (Tackling Drug Abuse: Challenges and the Way Forward." 2019)

The government of Sierra Leone has taken steps to fight drug misuse, realizing how severe the issue is. One move in the direction of reducing drug usage and trafficking was the creation of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA). There are still issues with staffing, infrastructure, and resources, though. With an emphasis on youth education, rehabilitation programs, and community outreach activities, civil

society organizations like Youth Partnership for Peace and Development (YPPD) and Caritas Sierra Leone have been actively involved in the prevention of drug misuse. (Drug Abuse and Youth in Post-Conflict Sierra Leone." 2018)

Substance usage, particularly with regard to drugs like cocaine, Kush, and Tramadol, has been connected to a rise in mental health problems in Sierra Leone, such as depression, schizophrenia, and anxiety. Drug misuse and criminal activity are closely associated, especially small-time larceny and gang-related violence. Drug-related violence frequently results from conflicts in the drug trade or from addicts trying to support their addictions with money. Abuse of drugs, especially injectable drugs, increases the risk of infectious disease transmission, including HIV/AIDS. (Annual Drug Report 2017)

Literature Review

A substance is a chemical that is used to improve one's physical and mental health or to treat, cure, prevent, or diagnose an illness (Rice & Dolgin, 2008). Chronic or frequent use of any chemical substance to change one's physical or mental state aside from uses authorized by medicine that has an adverse effect on one's own physical or mental health or the welfare of others is referred to as substance abuse (Drug Addiction and Drug Abuse, 2008). Nwika (1972) defined a drug as a material, an element, a compound, or a mixture that is used medicinally to alter the condition of the human body's cells, tissues, or organs, or in another organism. Such a material may be created alone or in conjunction with conversely, the use of medications against medical advice or prescriptions is known as drug abuse. The drug may be administered too much or too little, which over time might cause tolerance or even lead to drug addiction. (Michael Olusegun Adejimi, 2021)

Conversely, the use of medications against medical advice or prescriptions is known as drug abuse. The drug may be administered too much or too little, which over time might cause tolerance or even lead to drug addiction.

Mental Health

In the absence of mental disease, Manwell et al. (2015) defined mental health concerns as the biological, psychological, and social elements that may impact an individual's mental state and ability to operate in society. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2014), a person's capacity to manage typical life events and make a positive contribution to society is referred to as their mental health. Suicidal thoughts or depressive feelings throughout the previous two weeks were the dependent variables used to evaluate mental health issues. (MIYHS, 2017)

According to Cheng et al. (2014) and Manwell et al. (2015), mental health issues are a major public health concern and account for a large portion of the disease burden among young people in society. According to Cheng et al. (2014), mental health refers to a person's whole state of wellbeing, which includes their capacity to realize their full potential, manage stress in their daily lives, be productive, and give back to their communities. Adolescent mental health issues are thought to have a significant correlation with adult mental health issues. Both biological and psychosocial factors may have an impact on these health issues (Cheng et al., 2014; WHO, 2014). Genetic, cognitive, temperamental, interpersonal, and familial environment risk factors are additional elements that impact mental health (Cheng et al., 2014). As young adults, mental health (Cheng et al., 2014)

Social Support

An individual's formal or informal contact with another person (Joni & Leonard, 2013). Informal social support is that which originates from friends, family, and peers; formal social support is that which originates from organizations and medical experts. (Joni & Leonard, 2013)

An important component in assisting a person in adjusting to life changes is social support (Wang et al., 2017). In times of hardship, social support can help to reduce anxiety and offer hope (Cheng et al., 2014). Children and young people, particularly those exposed to traumatic life events, might suffer greatly from a lack of social support (Cheng et al., 2014). Reducing sorrow and fostering hope may be achieved by offering social assistance within the family and the community. Early in adulthood, social support is essential (Holden et al., 2015). People who cut themselves off from social networks run the danger of getting sick. (Levula&Harre, 2016)

The link between Substance and Mental Health Disorder

Dual diagnosis is rather common, according to an analysis done on patients receiving treatment for both mental health and substance use disorders (Di Lorenzo et al., 2014). It has long been disputed how substance misuse and mental health issues are related to one another and which condition initiates the other. Analyzing treatment plans, potential problems, and the study participants' needs for support with care were the study's objectives. This study comes to the conclusion that in order to concentrate on screening instruments, damage-reducing therapies, and ongoing support, it is necessary to understand the connection between substance misuse and mental disorders. Making ensuring that patients or clients are appropriately screened to identify if they have a dual diagnosis can guarantee that they receive a. (Crystal Ann Horton, 2017)

According to Watkins et al. (2014), people in substance addiction treatment programs were not currently receiving mental health care, despite the frequency of mental health disorders among clients who have entered an outpatient treatment program. According to the literature, patients who have had little access to therapy in the past may benefit from being identified as co-occurring disorder patients when they begin treatment. To properly treat the full person, people must be evaluated for both mental health conditions and substance abuse. It is the responsibility of the mental health professional or social worker to appropriately screen the patient and place them in an integrated program that addresses both of their needs, regardless of whether the patient wants treatment for substance misuse or mental health issues.(Horton, 2017)

Factors Influencing Abuse of Substances

Low socioeconomic status was linked to higher rates of drug and alcohol misuse, according to Goodman and Huang (2002). According to research by Goodman and Huang (2002), higher levels of teenage depression were linked to lower parental education and household income. Friestad et al. (2003) discovered a correlation between higher adolescent smoking rates and moderate home income and low parental education.

Reinherz and colleagues (2000) examined 360 respondents who were followed from 1977 to 2000 and discovered that a higher likelihood of drug abuse problems in early adulthood was associated with bigger family sizes and lower family socioeconomic status. According to a 2009 investigation by Hamilton and colleagues, teenagers (ages 12 to 19) who have parents who attended college are less likely to use illegal drugs or drink in a risky or harmful way.

Using illegal drugs is a high-risk habit that can have both short-term and long-term effects on one's mental health. Individual risk factors are undoubtedly linked to mental health problems, but sociodemographic factors also influence risky drug use behavior and the negative effects of drug use on mental health (Scher et al., 2004).

Individual mental health is frequently negatively impacted by the coincidence and interaction of these sociodemographic characteristics, which include age, race, ethnicity, and language, and the socioeconomic status, which includes income and education. The creation of health disparities between drug users and the general population is also significantly influenced by these sociodemographic characteristics (Scher et al., 2004).

According to a study by Taplin et al. (2014), compared to lower rates observed in the community and general population, the proportion of chronic injection substance users who had experienced any childhood abuse or neglect was incredibly high (72.9%). This indicates that there is a direct correlation between parental drug and alcohol usage and the intensity of childhood trauma. All forms of childhood trauma, with the exception of physical abuse, were significantly linked to maternal alcohol abuse; physical abuse was also linked to father alcohol addiction. According to Taplin et al. (2014), a significant contributing factor to the heightened severity of particular types of childhood trauma is drug addiction by the mother or father.

Ani (2015) found in her study that a number of factors affect substance usage among those who have mental health issues. According to the study, 32 drug usage is significantly correlated with respondents' parents' educational attainment and the kind of dwelling they occupied. The report went on to say that there is a substantial correlation between the user's educational level, drug and alcohol usage, and the kind of home they reside in. The study clearly showed that drug abusers are more likely to live with their parents than with other relatives. Substance misuse has been linked in the past to lower levels of educational achievement and labor market productivity (hart, Ksir, & Ray 2009).

Particularly, binge drinking has been connected to population-wide unintentional fatalities and driving while intoxicated (DUI). Due to the fact that illegal drugs are prohibited and using them increases the chance of mental illness in users. Substance abuse can therefore have serious detrimental effects on young adults. However, research has also demonstrated that marijuana's detrimental effects on attention, memory, and learning can persist for days or weeks after the drug's immediate effects wear off. This is significant because a large body of prior material has concentrated on the substance use of teenagers from lower-income backgrounds (Norman et al., 2003). As a result, a daily marijuana user may be operating mostly or entirely at a lower intellectual capacity.

Effects of Substance Abuse

Substance misuse has serious negative effects on one's social, economic, and health. Aside from the addicts themselves, the detrimental effects of substance usage extend to friends, family, businesses, and government resources. The current social systems are severely impacted by substance addiction and dependence, which also quickly depletes public coffers and impacts crime rates, child maltreatment and neglect, and public funding (Hoffman & Goldfrank, 1990). A substance's precise effects vary depending on what kind of substance is used, how much is taken, how it is taken, and how each person reacts. Substance abuse may be quite dangerous, and developing a dependency on them is not difficult.

Research Methodology

The data gathered using primary and secondary research approaches served as the foundation for the study's results. The study was conducted in Bo City, and a comprehensive strategy that combined qualitative and quantitative data collection methods was used to collect and analyze the data. In addition, the researcher recorded events and spoke with 275 people, including youths, community members, and stakeholders. The secondary data were obtained from academic journals, news articles, and other pertinent publications related to the subject under investigation.

Key Findings on Drug Abuse and Mental Health in Sierra Leone

These results suggest that socio-demographic factors should be taken into consideration when assessing substance addiction among those who suffer from serious mental illnesses. Young adults and men are most likely to abuse drugs. Patients who were widowed or divorced had lower rates of substance addiction than single patients, but married individuals had higher rates than single patients. This was consistent with other research (Robichaud, 2003; Tuchman, 2010) on the differences between genders in the frequency of mental illnesses and drug usage. Another aspect of substance misuse is the type of dwelling. Tenant housing typically declines to accept tenants that exhibit disruptive activities (Lynch et al., 2000). However, patients who reside in independent living are more likely to have drug users in their

(Lynch et al., 2000)

There is a strong correlation between education and substance misuse in terms of education. In contrast to patients with no formal education, those with tertiary education had a lower likelihood of abusing substances. This is most likely a result of awareness of the risks associated with substance abuse. Another demographic factor that affects substance addiction is work opportunity, as there is a correlation between substance misuse and employment opportunities. Compared to patients who were jobless, patients who were self-employed tended to be less prone to take drugs. Additionally, compared to patients who were unemployed, patients who worked as civil servants had a lower likelihood of abusing substances.

There is no conclusive link between religion and drug usage. This could be explained by the strong disapproval of alcohol drinking and illicit drug use held by the two main religions in Sierra Leone, Islam and Christianity in particular. Given that patients who misuse substances are more likely than non-abusers to suffer from major depression or bipolar disorder, the findings of the study reveal an unexpected link between substance abuse and the absence of mood disorders in these patients. Grella et al. (2009) claim that patients with mental disorders are more likely to consume substances.

The study's findings also demonstrate a strong correlation between substance misuse and anxiety disorders. Patients who abuse substances are less likely than non-abusers to experience significant depressive disorders and anxiety disorders, which helps to explain the association between substance abuse and anxiety disorders among users with mental health concerns. Moreover, individuals with serious mental illnesses who are unmarried and live alone may be driven to take drugs or alcohol in an attempt to cope with their loneliness (Segun et al., 2006). Additionally, there is a strong correlation between a history of violence and substance dependence. When seriously drunk, persons with significant mental illnesses who abuse substances are more likely to act violently or aggressively.

Lastly, the literature now in publication helps to elucidate the connection between substance addiction and social support among users who also have mental health concerns. This is a result of the social support records being absent from the patient's case file. Compared to patients who abuse substances, those who do not abuse substances typically receive more support from friends and family. Improved outcomes for individuals with co-occurring mental and substance abuse disorders are predicted by family and social supports, which also have an impact on treatment pursuit and admission (Moos & Moos 2007). An alternative hypothesis is that patients' inhibitions were lowered by drug and alcohol use.

Summary of Key Findings

Prior research has indicated a correlation between substance addiction and mental health issues. People who no longer have the support of friends and family from their social network may suffer the negative effects of substance misuse and use, which could negatively impact their overall health. Nonetheless, this study demonstrated that early detection of mental health issues in adolescents can lead to early intervention, which can help young people grow into more useful members of society. The study's conclusions demonstrated how a lack of social support may contribute to drug use and misuse as well as have an impact on young people's wellbeing.

Additionally, this study discovered that the main demographic and socioeconomic factors influencing substance usage among users with mental health difficulties include gender, age, employment position, education, and type of housing. Therefore, mental health providers should pay special attention to these factors where there may be a higher likelihood of substance misuse problems in persons. Furthermore, the findings indicate that severe mental problems, including schizophrenia and mood disorders, are clinical determinants of substance usage among substance users. Prioritizing services for mental health patients should include integrated dual diagnosis care, day hospitals, supervised housing, and assertive community therapy.

Moreover, different characteristics are linked to substance usage in males and girls with severe mental problems. It is critical that mental health professionals concentrate their efforts on young people who are living alone, have attempted suicide in the past, and have a violent past.

More research on the mental health issues connected to substance misuse should be done in the future, as well as research in a different community to validate the study's findings.

Recommendations

In light of the cross-sectional, retrospective, correlational methodology of the study, longitudinal and cohort studies are suggested for further research including young people. The assessment of the literature revealed that there were reports of mental health issues linked to substance use and social support in various communities and locations. According to the study's findings, early social support is advised as a potential preventative measure against adult mental health issues (Holden et al., 2015). It is also advised that practitioners create preventative programs for young people in school-age groups and concentrate on developing age-specific interventions for youth at risk for mental health disorders related to drug use.

The relevance of mental health among young adults is highlighted by the study's findings that substance usage is linked to certain clinical characteristics and psychological wellbeing. Therefore, the psychological well-being measure may be utilized in further studies to determine which teenagers are more likely to develop substance misuse issues and related disorders if they have lower psychological well-being levels. The vicious tension-reduction circle of psychological problems leading to substance use and then Early intervention is necessary to break the vicious cycle of psychological issues leading to substance abuse and subsequent psychological decline. Given that young adults made up the bulk of the study's sample, people should be aware of the increased risk factors associated with substance abuse behavior in this demographic. It is important to educate kids about substance usage and draw attention to the dire consequences that can arise from it. The need for young adult treatment programs is growing, which is reflected in the rising costs associated with substance dependence. These services come at a huge expense, which puts a tremendous strain on the nation's economy and health system.

The study's findings imply that in addition to the crucial initiatives aimed at avoiding substance misuse, there should be initiatives that detect and counsel young people experiencing adverse life events and receiving minimal support from friends and family. This could potentially be a useful strategy to reduce drug abuse. Expert training on substance abuse should be provided to all parties involved, especially parents and young adults. Therefore, this study suggests holding workshops on substance abuse education for both individuals and patients. They will be able to learn about the types of substance misuse, their warning signs and symptoms, and the resources in their local communities that can help users, particularly those who are struggling with mental health concerns, by doing this.

These training sessions, though, need to be customized to the participants' educational and cultural backgrounds. Lessons must include thorough knowledge about substances, and workshops, campaigns, and awareness initiatives regarding substance usage must be put into place. It is important to arrange site visits to hospitals and rehabilitation facilities whenever feasible so that people can observe the struggles faced by substance abusers.

When patients face challenging circumstances in their lives, they should be taught coping mechanisms and rejection techniques (Partnership for a Drug-Free America, 2009). In addition, support groups ought to be formed nationwide to offer assistance and companionship to individuals undergoing mental health disorders.

To curb drug use and trafficking, Sierra Leone must strengthen its legal and regulatory framework and make sure that the laws are correctly applied. Increased funding is required for mental health and rehabilitation programs, with an emphasis on DE stigmatizing drug abuse and providing assistance to victims and survivors. Reducing the allure of drugs can be achieved by addressing the underlying socioeconomic issues, such as unemployment and low education, and by offering job opportunities, mentorship, and vocational training. The National Drug Control Act of 2008 is one of the laws that Sierra Leone has in place to combat drug usage and trafficking. Unfortunately, insufficient funding and corruption have made implementation difficult. Organizations that strive to increase awareness include the Sierra Leone Drug Prevention Network and the West African Drug Policy Network.

Conclusion

We can conclude that the main demographic and socioeconomic factors influencing substance abuse among users with mental health disorders are age, gender, type of housing, education, employment status, and type of housing. Therefore, mental health providers should pay special attention to these factors where there may be a higher likelihood of substance misuse problems in persons. The findings also show a link between substance usage and serious mental illnesses, such as schizophrenia; among other things, mood disorders are clinical determinants of substance abuse in this study. Prioritizing services for mental health patients should include integrated dual diagnosis care, day hospitals, supervised housing, and assertive community therapy.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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